

ANALYSIS OF ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS IN FERGANA REGION

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Annotation. *One of the main current and future issues is ensuring road safety, which is aimed at reducing the number of road accidents, the number of fatalities and injuries, and the overall socio-economic damage caused.*

Keywords: *traffic safety, road traffic accident, vehicle*

INTRODUCTION

The organization of traffic safety on roads is becoming one of the most important problems today. The amount of damage caused by cars to the environment is increasing day by day, and the most important thing is that many people are injured and lose their lives as a result of road accidents. Despite a number of measures taken to prevent road accidents, their number cannot be reduced. This makes it necessary for experts to take the problems of road safety very seriously. To ensure traffic safety, it is necessary to take a scientific approach to it, analyze all its complex processes. To do this, traffic safety specialists need to have knowledge of the main indicators of traffic, how road conditions affect the movement of traffic flows, and how to manage traffic through technical means of traffic flow management [1].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

A number of educational literature and scientific sources serve as the main theoretical and methodological basis for studying the processes of ensuring road safety, effectively organizing traffic flow, and designing highways. In particular, the textbook by Q.H. Azizov entitled "Fundamentals of organizing traffic safety" extensively covers such important aspects as modern principles of organizing road traffic, behavior of traffic participants, methods of control using technical means, technical condition of vehicles, and the role of the driver in traffic safety. It describes practical measures for road safety based on advanced foreign experience and technical achievements [6-7].

RESULTS

According to the World Health Organization, approximately 1.19 million people die in road accidents every year. In Uzbekistan alone, in 2024, 9,364 road accidents occurred in our country, resulting in 2,203 deaths.

Despite the positive work being done in our country to ensure road safety due to the growth of motorization, the current situation requires us to improve our work in

this area, study and implement the best practices of foreign countries, and train qualified drivers to ensure road safety [3].

While driving a vehicle, a driver must ensure the smooth movement of other vehicles on the road, communicate with road users, and comply with traffic rules. Modernization and development of road transport infrastructure is of great importance in ensuring road safety. Road traffic rules include mandatory requirements applicable to all individuals and citizens and are aimed at ensuring the safety and health of citizens.

According to the Department of Road Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, during the first 12 months of 2023, 9,839 road accidents occurred in Uzbekistan, in which 2,282 citizens died and about 9,209 were injured. During the last 12 months of 2024, 9,364 road accidents occurred, in which 2,203 citizens died and 8,901 citizens were injured to varying degrees. Analysis shows that the main cause of road accidents that resulted in the deaths of 2,203 citizens was 52.3% of drivers' gross violation of traffic rules [2].

INFORMATION on traffic accidents committed during 2023-2024

31.12.2024to the day of the year	Year	Total RT A	Injuries	Died	With the participation of children			Hitting a pedestrian		
					Total RT A	Injuries	Died	Total RT A	Injuries	Died
Group 1										
Fergana region	2024 2023	173 158	157 139	16 19	33 29	32 28	2 1	94 70	88 63	7 8
Increase/decrease		15	18	-3	4	4	1	24	25	-1
Increase/decrease %		9,5	12,9	-15,8	13,8	14,3	100,0	34,3	39,7	-12,5
Group 2										
Margilan	2024	114 115	107 105	7 10	26 31	24 28	2 3	60 62	55 56	6 6

	2023									
Increase/decrease		-1	2	-3	-5	-4	-1	-2	-1	0
Increase/decrease %		-0,9	1,9	-30,0	-16,1	-14,3	-33,3	-3,2	-1,8	0,0
Tashlok	2024 2023	73 69	66 58	7 11	25 24	22 21	3 3	37 23	37 21	0 2
Increase/decrease		4	8	-4	1	1	0	14	16	-2
Increase/decrease %		5,8	13,8	-36,4	4,2	4,8	0,0	60,9	76,2	0,0
Yazvoyon	2024 2023	57 65	48 56	9 9	15 9	14 8	1 1	15 13	15 10	0 3
Increase/decrease		-8	-8	0	6	6	0	2	5	-3
Increase/decrease %		-12,3	-14,3	0,0	66,7	75,0	0,0	15,4	50,0	0,0
Total Group 2	2024	224	221	23	66	60	6	112	107	6
	2023	249	219	30	64	57	7	98	87	11
Increase/decrease		-5	2	-7	2	3	-1	14	20	-5
Increase/decrease %		-2,0	0,9	-23,3	3,1	5,3	-14,3	14,3	23,0	-45,5
Group 3										
Altyariq	2024	84 81	63 66	21 15	21 18	17 16	4 3	31 32	20 27	11 8

	2023									
Increase/decrease		3	-3	6	3	1	1	-1	-7	3
Increase/decrease %		3,7	-4,5	40,0	16,7	6,3	33,3	-3,1	-25,9	37,5
Kushtepa district	2024 2023	43 54	33 44	10 10	9 11	9 10	0 1	13 20	9 17	4 4
Increase/decrease		-11	-11	0	-2	-1	-1	-7	-8	0
Increase/decrease %		-20,4	-25,0	0,0	-18,2	-10,0	0,0	-35,0	-47,1	0,0
Sokh district	2024 2023	2 6	0 4	2 2	0 2	0 2	0 0	0 4	0 3	0 1
Increase/decrease		-4	-4	0	-2	-2	0	-4	-3	-1
Increase/decrease %		-66,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Total Group 3	2024	129	96	33	30	26	4	44	29	15
	2023	141	114	27	31	28	4	56	47	13
Increase/decrease		-12	-18	6	-1	-2	0	-12	-18	2
Increase/decrease %		-8,5	-15,8	22,2	-3,2	-7,1	0,0	-21,4	-38,3	15,4
Fergana	2024 2023	54 54	40 39	14 15	16 9	16 7	1 2	22 26	19 23	3 3
Increase/decrease		0	1	-1	7	9	-1	-4	-4	0

Increase/decrease %		0,0	2,6	-6,7	77,8	128,6	-50,0	-15,4	-17,4	0,0
Quvasoy sh	2024 2023	3128	2421	77	74	53	21	106	84	22
Increase/decrease		3	3	0	3	2	1	4	4	0
Increase/decrease %		10,7	14,3	0,0	75,0	66,7	100,0	66,7	100,0	0,0
Kuva	2024 2023	8486	6969	1517	2518	2417	11	3228	3025	23
Increase/decrease		-2	0	-2	7	7	0	4	5	-1
Increase/decrease %		-2,3	0,0	-11,8	38,9	41,2	0,0	14,3	20,0	-33,3
Total Group 4	2024 2023	169168	133129	3639	4831	4527	44	6460	5752	78
Increase/decrease		1	4	-3	17	18	0	4	5	-1
Increase/decrease %		0,6	3,1	-7,7	54,8	66,7	0,0	6,7	9,6	-12,5
1-RTA squad total	2024 2023	715716	607601	108115	177155	163140	1616	314284	281249	3540
Increase/decrease %		-1	6	-7	22	23	0	30	32	-5
Increase/decrease %		-0,1	1,0	-6,1	14,2	16,4	0,0	10,6	12,9	-12,5

When analyzing road traffic accidents in the Qoshtepa district, the number of road traffic accidents in the district in 2024 compared to 2023 decreased by (54-43) - 11 or -20.4 percent. However, in some urban districts of the region, including Fergana city, the number of road traffic accidents increased by (158-173) +15 or 9.5 percent. In Oltiariq district, the number of road traffic accidents increased by (81-84) +3 or 3.7 percent. In Toshlok district, the number of road traffic accidents increased by (69-73) +4 or 5.8 percent. In Jalaquduk district, the number of road traffic accidents increased by (28-31) +3 or 10.7 percent [4].

DISCUSSION

Extensive organizational and practical work has been carried out in our country to improve the road safety system. At the same time, despite the measures taken, the number of fatal road accidents is still high, indicating the need for a fundamental reform of the road safety system.

In order to ensure the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Road Safety", as well as to further improve the Rules of the Road, prevent road accidents, control and increase the effectiveness of road safety in accordance with the requirements of the 1968 Vienna Convention on Road Traffic and advanced foreign experience, a number of laws have been studied.

Establish a procedure according to which:

in populated areas, the speed of vehicles is allowed to exceed 60 kilometers per hour, on roads around schools and preschool educational institutions - 30 kilometers per hour within a distance of 300 meters, and in residential areas and adjacent areas (on land plots between residential buildings) - 20 kilometers per hour.

➤ In this regard, based on the resolution of the Republican Commission for Road Safety, established by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to reliably ensure human safety on roads and sharply reduce fatalities" dated April 4, 2022 No. PQ-190, the maximum speed of vehicles in the cities of Tashkent and Nukus and regional centers with high traffic and densely populated areas may be set at 60 kilometers per hour:

➤ Transportation of goods in passenger cars is allowed if the height of the cargo in the luggage compartment installed on their roof does not exceed 1 meter (except for the transportation of bicycles reinforced with special devices) and the length does not exceed the dimensions of the car by 0.5 meters;

➤ Trucks, in all cases, with some exceptions specified in the Traffic Rules, must move only on the right carriageway;

It is prohibited to stop vehicles at turning points and within 30 meters of them or beyond them;

Cyclists traveling on the carriageway of the road without a bicycle lane at night and in conditions of insufficient visibility must wear a reflective vest or outerwear with reflective elements [1].

"Ensuring traffic safety on highways and city streets remains one of the main pressing problems. An analysis of road accidents over the past decade shows that their average annual number does not fall below 10-11 thousand, resulting in the deaths of two thousand citizens of our Republic and the injury of 10-12 thousand people [1].

CONCLUSION

The increase in the number of passenger cars in the population, in general, the smoothness of roads, the use of road signs, the operation of traffic lights, improving traffic on the roads, and preventing road traffic accidents and various unfortunate incidents are becoming important problems.

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